

Milestone:

MS18 - Third technical expert seminar held

Lead Participant:

UU

Author:

Anna Hagwall

Due:

June 2025

Date Of Completion:

2025-06-13

Means of Verification

Workshop in Brno, CZ, 2--4 September 2024.

Main themes were responsibilities of and expectations on different pillars and countries on different deployment stages, interoperability, SOPs, MVP, MS8, and discussions on difficulties.

Folder with agenda:

<https://docs.google.com/document/u/o/d/1QoUkxZDyuBy3moyA22X-ygUR3nSSFy7ZttCzFGhf8lw/edit>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

The work was done prior to and during September 2024. The slides were finalized in June 2025, at the time of the deadline.

Project participants & others

About 90 persons from 22 countries, the ELIXIR Hub and the European commission participated.

As last time, we included sessions on data management and not only systems development.

The meeting was facilitated by UU (task 5.1 leads and WP3 leads). The agenda was co-created by WP leads in pillar II. The hosts in CZ arranged the venue and logistics.

Next action steps

Milestone 8 was the major imminent next step.

Also, identify what can be technically ready by the end of the project. (Discussed and defined in spring 2025)
Next workshop is in October 2025.

